

Studies on some Thioindigoids and Related Compounds Part IV

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3-Hydroxy-7-bromothionaphthene has been synthesised and condensed with various acenaphthenequinones, phenanthraquinone, and three aromatic aldehydes. The colour, dyed shade, and absorption maxima of some of the resulting thioindigoids and thioindogenides of the 7-bromo series on comparison with those of the available corresponding 5-bromo¹ compounds, previously studied, clearly indicated that 7-bromo dyes are lighter in colour.

For the present investigation, the details of the preparation of the starting material, 3-hydroxy-7-bromothionaphthene, was at first worked out following the route: *o*-bromoaniline → *o*-bromophenylthioglycolic acid → 3-hydroxy-7-bromothionaphthene. Subsequently, thioindigoid dyes and thioindogenides were obtained.

2-(7-Bromo)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene Indigos (I, a-d).

These dyestuffs were obtained by condensing 3-hydroxy-7-bromothionaphthene with acenaphthenequinone, its 3-bromo-, 1-methoxy-, and 3,4-dinitro derivative respectively. These are red, darkish red and darkish violet substances, crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. above 300° and obtained in 60-75% yield. These are soluble in benzene, nitrobenzene, acetic acid, and chloroform except the dinitro dye (Id) which is moderately soluble in benzene and chloroform. The compound (Ia) is moderately soluble in ethanol and the rest are very sparingly soluble in the same solvent.

The symmetrical dye, 7:7'-dibromothioindigo² (II) was prepared from a pure specimen of 3-hydroxy-7-bromothionaphthene for comparison with the 5:5'-dibromo³ analogue and crystallised from nitrobenzene as darkish violet dye melting above 300°. It is soluble in aniline, sparingly soluble in acetic acid and insoluble in ethanol.

Another thioindigoid dye, 2-(7-bromo)-thionaphthene-9'-phenanthreneindigo (III) was synthesised as a dark violet crystalline substance for comparison with the colour of the compound (Ia) which is red. It is soluble in benzene, acetic acid, and sparingly soluble in ethanol.

1. Guha and Chatterjee, *Chem. Ber.*, 1959, 92, 2768.
2. Dokunikhin and Geradimenko, *Zhur. Obsh. Khim.*, 1960, 36, 1967.
3. G. P. 225133; Guha and Banerji, *this Journal*, 1959, 36, 680.

A comparison of colour, dyed shade and absorption maxima of some of the 7-bromo dyes, cited above, with those of the available corresponding 5-bromo dyes reported already, convince that 7-bromo dyes are lighter in colour (Table I).

Benzylidene-2-(7-bromo)-thionaphthenes (IV)

(IV)

- a : R = H
 b : R = NO₂
 c : R = NMe₂

These thioindogenides were obtained by condensing 3-hydroxy-7-bromothionaphthene with benzaldehyde, its *p*-nitro-, and *p*-dimethylamino derivative respectively. These are yellow, deep yellow, and yellowish red crystalline products from ethanol and are soluble in chloroform, ethanol, acetic acid, benzene, nitrobenzene, and xylene. No effort was made to develop their dyeing shade on cotton as these cannot be reduced by alkaline hydrosulphite. Their colour and absorption maxima indicate clearly that these 7-bromo compounds are lighter in colour than the corresponding 5-bromo products.¹ (Table I).

TABLE I

	$\lambda_{\max}$
2-(7-bromo)-T-AI	518.0 m μ
2-(5-bromo)-T-AI	.. 524.0
2-T-AI	.. 477.5
2-(7-bromo)-T-8'-(1'-methoxy)-AI	.. 526
2-(5-bromo)-T-8'-(1'-methoxy)-AI	.. 534
2-T-8'-(1'-methoxy)-AI	.. 524
7:7'-dibromo-thioindigo	.. 548*
5:5'-dibromo-thioindigo	.. 562**
Thioindigo	.. 525
B-2-(7-bromo)-T	.. 438
B-2-(5-bromo)-T	.. 446
B-2-T	.. 434
4'-Dimethylamino-B-2-(7-bromo)-T	.. 490
4'-Dimethylamino-B-2-(5-bromo)-T	.. 494
4'-Dimethylamino-B-2-T	.. 478

N.B.—T denotes thionaphthene; AI denotes azensaphthylene-indigo; B denotes benzylidene.

* Dokunikhin² found maxima at 546 m μ .

**G.P.³ recorded 555.5 λ (m μ) and Dokunikhin found maxima at 559 m μ .

For the uniformity and right comparison, the $\lambda_{\max}$ data for the isomeric 5:5'- and 7:7'-dibromothioindigos were redetermined in xylene solution with authentic specimen prepared now.

4. Guha and Chatterjee, *this Journal*, 1951, 23, 108.

It is also concluded that the introduction of a bromine atom in 5-, and 7- position of the thionaphthene ring of the parent compound of each series stated above deepens the colour, running in the order: 5-Br > 7-Br > Parent dye.

EXPERIMENTAL

o-Bromophenyl thioglycollic Acid.—A solution of sodium nitrite (8.4 g.) in water (15 ml.) was added dropwise to a well-stirred mixture of 17.2 g *o*-bromoaniline (17.2 g.), HCl (conc., 30 ml.), and water (90 ml.) maintained at 0-2°. The diazo solution was then gradually added during 20 min. to a stirred solution of ethyl potassium xanthate (24.2 g.), anhydrous sodium carbonate (50 g.) and water (200 ml.) previously kept at 60-80°. After stirring for 1 hr. more, the entire solution was allowed to stand overnight and then extracted with ether which when removed left a crude oily product. It was boiled under reflux, with a mixture NaOH (21 g.), water (50 ml.), and ethanol (150 ml) for 2 hrs. A solution of monochloroacetic acid (20 g. in 10% aq. NaOH, 85 ml.) was then cautiously added and boiling continued for further 30 min. The alcohol was distilled; the residual solution was added to crushed ice. The acid was precipitated by slow addition of HCl (conc.). It was crystallised from hot water (charcoal), m.p. 119-20°, yield 14.8 g. (60%). (Found: C, 38.96; H, 2.95. $C_8H_7O_2BrS$ requires C, 38.88; H, 2.89%).

3-Hydroxy-7-bromothionaphthene.—The preceding acid (1.8g.) was cyclised in dry benzene (30 ml.) solution by P_2O_5 (10 g.) by refluxing on a water bath for 4 hrs. It was cooled and decomposed by ice. After removal of the benzene, the thioindoxyl was obtained by superheated steam as colorless needles, yield 0.44 g. (27%). It was recrystallised from light petroleum, m.p. 108°. (Found: C, 42.42; H, 2.31. $C_8H_5O BrS$ requires C, 41.93; H, 2.19%). The condensation of the 7-bromo products (vide *infra*) was carried out in the same manner as the 5-bromo compounds described earlier.*

2-(7-Bromo)thionaphthene-acenaphthylene indigo (Ia) was obtained from acenaphthenequinone (0.09 g.) and HBT* (0.115 g.) as soft silky fine red needles, yield 0.15 g. (76%). Strong sulphuric acid dissolves it producing a bottle-green solution. Cotton is dyed in red shade from a violet vat. (Found: C, 61.32; H, 2.52. $C_{20}H_9O_2BrS$ requires C, 61.08; H, 2.3%).

2-(7-Bromo)thionaphthene-8'-(3'-bromo)acenaphthylene indigo (Ib) was obtained from 3-bromo-acenaphthenequinone (0.13 g.) and HBT (0.115 g.) as red crystals, yield 0.177 g. (75%). A bluish green solution is produced when treated with H_2SO_4 (conc.). A red shade is developed on cotton from a violet blue vat. (Found: C, 51.18; H, 1.19. $C_{20}H_8O_2Br_2S$ requires C, 50.87; H, 1.71%).

2-(7-Bromo)thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy)acenaphthylene indigo (Ic) was prepared from 1-methoxy-acenaphthenequinone (0.105g.) and HBT (0.115 g.) as darkish red crystals, yield 0.16 g. (75%). The solution of the substance in H_2SO_4 (conc.) is blue. It developed a pink shade on cotton from a violet vat. (Found: C, 59.82; H, 2.92. $C_{21}H_{11}O_2BrS$ requires C, 59.59; H, 2.82%).

2-(7-Bromo)thionaphthene-8'-(3',4'-dinitro)acenaphthylene indigo (Id) was obtained from 3,4-dinitroacenaphthenequinone (0.186 g.) and HBT (0.115 g.) as darkish violet dye,

*For brevity, HBT denotes 3-hydroxy-7-bromo thionaphthene.

yield 0.144 g. (80%). H_2SO_4 (conc.) dissolves it forming a yellowish green solution. A light darkish violet shade was obtained on cotton from yellowish red vat. (Found: N, 6.26. $C_{20}H_8O_6BrN_2S$ requires N, 6.79%).

7, 7'-*Dibromothioindigo* (II) was prepared from HBT (0.23g.) by oxidation by alkaline potassium ferriocyanide as darkish violet crystals, yield 0.16 g. (72 %). A light blue solution is produced on treatment with H_2SO_4 (conc.). Its dyed shade on cotton was violet from a yellow vat. (Found: C, 42.71. H, 1.72. Calc. for $C_{16}H_6O_4Br_2S_2$: C, 42.31; H, 1.33%).

2-(7-*Bromo*)thionaphthene-9'-*phenanthrene indigo* (III) was obtained from phenanthraquinone (0.104g.) and HBT (0.115 g.) as dark violet crystals, yield 0.095 g. (45 %). It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 274-75°. On treatment with H_2SO_4 (conc.) a green solution was obtained. (cf. 7-chlorodyo⁴). The dyed shade on cotton was light violet from a yellow vat. (Found: C, 63.42. H, 2.80. $C_{22}H_{11}O_4BrS$ requires C, 63.01; H, 2.64 %).

Benzylidene-2-(7-*bromo*)thionaphthene (IVa) was prepared from pure benzaldehyde (0.05g.) and HBT (0.115 g.) as yellow crystals, yield 0.105 g. (70%); m.p. 162°. It dissolves in H_2SO_4 (conc.) forming a blood-red solution. (Found: C, 56.85; H, 3.05. $C_{15}H_9OBrS$ requires C, 56.79; H, 2.86%).

4'-*Nitrobenzylidene*-2-(7-*bromo*)thionaphthene (IVb) was obtained from *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde (0.075 g.) and HBT (0.115g.) as deep yellow crystals, yield 0.127 g (70%), m.p. 261-82°. The solution of the substance in H_2SO_4 (conc.) is violet-blue. (Found: N, 4.31. $C_{15}H_8O_3BrNS$ requires N, 3.86%).

4'-*Dimethylaminobenzylidene*-2-(7-*bromo*)thionaphthene (IVc) was obtained from (0.075 g.) *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde and HBT (0.115g.) as yellowish red crystals, m.p. 164-85°, yield 0.09 g. (50%). H_2SO_4 (conc.) dissolves it for producing a violet colour. (Found: N, 4.1. $C_{17}H_{14}ONBrS$ requires N, 3.88%).

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